

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF ARDITA (BELL'S PALSY): A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Bell's palsy is an acute idiopathic lower motor neuron facial paralysis. Mainly characterized by sudden onset paralysis or weakness of the muscles to one side of face controlled by the facial nerve. In contemporary medicine steroids and antiviral medicine are choice of treatment. Symptoms of Bell's palsy similar to *Ardita* mentioned in *Ayurvedic* classics which is included amongst the eighty *Nanatmaja vata vikara* by *Acharya Charaka*. *Navana nasya* and *Nadi-sweda* are prime treatment modalities for *Ardita* described by *Acharya Charaka*. *Snehana* is considered best *Vata shamaka*. **Aim and objective:** There are Several works that has been done on *Ardita*. This study aimed to assess the efficacy of *Nasya*, *Shiropichu* and *kheerdhooma with Shamana Chikitsa* in the management of *Ardita*. **Material and Method:** A single case study of 68 years old male patient with left LMN left hemifacial palsy with symptoms of drooping of angle of mouth on left side, difficulty in speech, difficulty in wrinkling of forehead on left side, dribbling of food at the left side of the mouth and numbness in left side of face. He was treated with *Nasya* of 101 avarti

Ksheerabala taila in vardhamana matra, Shiropichu with Bala taila and Dashamoola ksheera dhuma Swedana. Result: After completion of treatment, the patient shown almost complete recovery without any adverse effect within 15 days. Thus, this whole treatment can prove to be effective in management of *Ardita* by reducing the symptoms and correcting the pathophysiology.

KEYWORDS: *Ardita*, Bell's palsy, *Nasya*, *Ksheeradharma*.

INTRODUCTION

Ardita is a disease in which there is a deviation leading to deformity of one side of the face alone or along with one side of the body.^[1]

Acharya Sushruta says that the mouth and other regions e.g. The head are affected while *Acharya Vagbhatta* says half of the face is involved with or without involvement of half of the body*. *Acharya Charaka* has described 80 types or *Vataj Nanatmaj Vyadhi*, *Ardita* is one among them.^[2] It can be correlated with the disease Bell's palsy most common cause of unilateral facial paralysis. It is also correlated with facial palsy or 7th Nerve palsy. Facial nerve is the 7th cranial nerve situated in pons lateral to root of 6th nerve. Bell's palsy is a LMN disease.^[3] Characterized by ache in the region of the stylomastoid foramen result in pressure on the nerve causing paralysis of function.

In *Ayurveda* it is explained as a specific disease afflicting the *Urdhavanga (Jatrurdhwa)* part above the neck particularly the face. And it is also an established fact that *Nasya* is one of the best measures to treat diseases manifested in *Jatrurdhwa*.^[4] *Ushna, Snigdha, Guru Gunas* needed for the treatment of *Ardita* can easily attained by *Navana, Tarpana, Moordha Taila, Nadi Sweda & Upanah Sweda* which is required to counter the *Ruksh, Sheeta, Laghu Gunas* of *Vata* which is predominate *Dosha* in the *Ardita*.^[5]

Bell's palsy has an incidence of 15 to 23 cases per 100,000 population/year, or about 1 in 60 to 70 people in a lifetime.^[6]

CASE HISTORY

A 68 years old male patient was apparently normal before 7 days but after continuous exposure to cold wind suddenly he noticed slight deviation of mouth to right side. next morning on 14th may 2023 gradually, he suffered from symptoms such as deviation of face on right side, unable to chew from left side, inability to blink left eye.

Chief Complaints

- Drooping of angle of mouth on left side
- Difficulty in speech
- Difficulty in wrinkling of forehead on left side
- Dribbling of food at the left side of the mouth
- Numbness in left side of face

Personal history

Diet: Mixed, Addiction: Smoking, Sleep: Regular, Occupation: Labourer

ASTHAVIDHA PARIKSHA

Nadi(pulse): 84/min	Mala(stool): 1time/day
Mutra(urine): 5-6times/day	Jihva(tongue): Nirama
Shabda(voice): Alpa Aspashta	Sparsh(touch): samsheetoshna
Netra(eyes): Raktabh pita	Akriti: Madhyam

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

BP: 110/70mmhg	HR: 76/min
PULSE: 84/min	RR:16/min

CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM EXAMINATION

1. Higher Motor Functions intact	2. Consciousness- Conscious
2. Orientation to- Time, place, person- Intact	4. Memory - Recent -not affected, Remote- not affected
5. Intelligence- Intact	6. Hallucination & Delusion - Absent
7. Speech - Slow and Slightly slurred	

Cranial Nerve Examinations Neurological exam noting functions of all other cranial nerves, aside from the facial nerve, are intact. Cerebellar examination is also normal.

a. Forehead frowning - not possible on left side	b. Eyebrow raising - not possible on left side
c. Eye closure - Left eyeball moves upwards and inwards when the patient attempts to close it along with incomplete closure of eyelid. (Bells phenomenon)	d. Teeth showing - not possible in left side denture
e. Blowing of cheek - not Possible in left side	f. Nasolabial fold - Naso labial fold loss on Left side.
g. Taste perception - not affected	h. Dribbling of saliva – Dribbling of saliva on Left angle of mouth and spilling of food contents during eating from left side
i. Bells phenomenon – present on left side	j. Deviation of mouth towards right side

Deep Reflexes such as Biceps, Triceps, Supinator, Knee jerk, Ankle jerk and Plantar reflex are normal. Muscle power and Muscle tone in all limbs are also normal.

SAMPRAPTI GHATAK

• Dosha: Vata	• Dushya: Rasa, Rakta, Sira, Mansa
• Adhistana: Mukhardha	• Srotasa: Rasavaha, Rakta Vaha, Mansavaha
• Sroto Dusti: Sang, Sira Granthi	• Agni: Vishamagni
• Vyadhi Svabhava: Navin	• Sadhyasadhya: Navin- Sadhya, Jirna-Yapya /Ashadhya

TEATMENT PLAN

DATE	DURATION	KARMA	SHAMANA CHIKITSA
21/5/2023 to 05/06/2023	15 Days	1. Sthanik Ahyanga with nirgundi taila 2. Dashmoola ksheeradhuma swedana	1. Cap. Palsinuron 1-0-1(After food) 2. Lashunadi vati 2-0-2(before food)
		3. Nasya karma with 101 avarti kheerabala taila in vardhaman matra (4,6...20,18,16...4) 4. Shiropichu with bala taila	3. Laghu yagraj guggulu 2-2-2 (After food) 4. Shatavari churna - 1 gm Ashwagandha churna - 1 gm Rasayan churna - 1gm Godanti Bhasma -250 mg (1 tds – 2 times/day with milk, after food) Advise: Balloon exercise

RESULT

Assessment was done on the basis of scoring of cardinal associated signs and observed symptoms. A facial nerve function grading by House-Brackmann grading measures was used to assess outcomes.^[7]

PARAMETERS	BEFORE (21/05/2023)	AFTER 7 DAYS (27/05/2023)	AFTER 15 DAYS (15/06/2023)
Daviation of mouth towards right side	Grade 4	Grade 2	Grade 1 (Decreased By 75 % Turning to Normal symmetry of face was able to wrinkle the forehead and raise the Eyebrows.)
Unable to chew from left side	Grade 3	Grade 2 (able to chew with difficulty)	Grade 0 (easily chew from left side)
Improper blinking of left eye	Grade 3	Grade 2	Grade 0 (Easily blink left eyelid)

Slurred speech	Grade 3	Grade 2 (Mild improves pronouncing with some efforts)	Grade 0 (Normal speech)
Dribbling of saliva	Grade 3 (Constant but mild dribbling)	Grade 2 (Intermittent dribbling)	Grade 0 (Dribbling absent now able to hold water in mouth and there was no dribbling of saliva.)
Smiling sign	Grade 3 (Smiling sign present with movement of right angle of mouth)	Grade 2 (Smiling sign present without upward movement of right of mouth)	Grade 0
Widening of palpebral aperture	Grade 4 Severely wide (cornea & ½ of upper sclera visible)	Grade 3 Moderately wide (cornea & 1/3 of upper sclera visible)	Grade 2 Slightly wide (Whole cornea visible)

100% relief was found in slurred speech, dribbling of saliva from left corner of mouth, 50% relief was found in widening of palpebral aperture and in smiling sign. Before starting the treatment, the House Brackmann's grading of facial nerve was Grade 4 and after commencement of 14 days treatment; it was Grade 2. There was no side effect observed during and after the treatment.

[BEFORE TREATMENT]

[AFTER TREATMENT]

- Note: above given picture was taken with the consent taken from patient.

DISCUSSION

The functions of sense organs impaired in Ardita (Bell's palsy), hence Ardita considered as a disorder of sense organ which are governed by the Omni presence of Vata. Acharya Charaka attributed the root cause of Ardita to highly vitiated Vata dosha. that's why Ardita requires a nourishing type of therapy as per acharya charaka and acharya vagbhatta. Nasya Karma, Moordha Taila, Tarpana with medicated oil to the eyes and ears, Nadi Sweda, Upanaha Sweda are included in the treatment principle of Ardita in ayurvedic classics.

Keeping all these efficacious treatment modalities in mind, *Nasya* of 101 avarti *Ksheerabala taila* in *vardhamana matra*, *Shiropichu* with *Bala taila* and *Dashamoola ksheera dhuma Swedana* was planned for the present case.

Abhyanga with nirgundi taila prior to Nasya karma nourishes the kapha stimulates the sensory nerve endings and provide strength to the facial muscle.

Swedana karma done with Dashamoola sidhha kheera it is coming under the variety of ushma sweda. Mild swedana before the Nasya karma and after facial massage enhance local microcirculation by dilation of blood vessels and increasing blood flow to the peripheral arterioles which accelerates the drug absorption and fast improvement. It also stimulates the local nerves and also provide strength to the facial muscle.

Kheerabala taila which is used for Nasya karma, is known for its bruhanakarma, which pacifies vata; it gives strength to the facial muscle and reduce any type of irritation of nerves. The constituents of kheerabala taila, that is bala (*Sida cordifolia* Linn.), milk and sesame oil, are well demonstrated to be antioxidants that prevent the possible damage of the neurons. Nasya drug acts on Shringatak marma^{viii} which is congruence of the nerve fibres of taste, smell, vision, speech and hearing sensation. Anatomically Shringatak marma taken as cavernous sinus. This sinus drains into the facial vein through the superior ophthalmic veins.

Shiropichu with Bala taila is also a nourishing therapy, which pacifies vata and improve the circulation there by correcting the brain circulation.

Capsule Palsinuron have many contains which promote healing of damaged nerve and blood vessels, recanalize blood vessels, activate sensory & motor functions. Laghu yogaraj guggulu act as bruhana, rasayana and vatahara which helps in enhancing the speed of recovery in the patients of Ardita. Other drug like Lashunadi vati is also having vataghna property. Godanti, shatavari, and ashwagandha powder are also used in this patient, which are helpful in rejuvenation of all Dhatus in the body. Exercise with balloon cause nerve stimulation and releases the compression of nerve.

CONCLUSION

From the present case study, it was observed that ayurvedic management described in classical text is helpful in giving significant relief in symptoms and signs of the disease Bell's palsy. All the therapy like Nasya, dashamoola ksheeradhuma swedana, shiropichu as a combined treatment, pacify the vitiated vata in the body and thus provide nourishment to the sense organs. Makeover the drugs used orally and exercise are having additional effect in relieving the signs and symptoms.

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